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Research Article

**FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND *IN-VITRO*
EVALUATION OF EXTENDED-RELEASE TABLETS
CONTAINING AZILSARTAN****Satyabrata Jena ^{1*}, Mohammad Sadik Khanushiya², Lalith Sagar Reddy Gade³,
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Moinabad, Hyderabad-500075⁶Principal, Bhaskar Pharmacy College, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Hyderabad-500075**Abstract:**

The current work was focused to formulate and evaluate extended release tablets of Azilsartan. Eudragit RL, Ethyl Cellulose and Carbopol p934 are matrix polymer can be used in formulation of extended release dosage form. Azilsartan was considered as ideal drug for extended release formulation. The extended release matrix of Azilsartan were prepared by direct compression method in differ matrix polymers ratio. Pre formulation studies have been performed for the Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient. Drug Excipient compatibility studies have been performed and the tablets have been prepared in eight different formulations with the change in the ratios of polymers. These tablets are evaluated for various parameters including the release of drug by using dissolution studies. Hence the study resulted in the development of Azilsartan extended release tablets F4 formulation was considered as optimized formulation. The Kinetic treatment of selected formulation F4 showed that the release of drug follows Zero order models.

Keywords: Azilsartan, Eudragit RL, Ethyl Cellulose, Carbopol p934 and extended release tablets.

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1.INTRODUCTION:

The vital role of novel drug delivery system that improve the therapeutic effectiveness of integrated drugs by providing extended, controlled delivery and or targeting the drug to desired site. Extended-release formulations make the drug available over extended time period after oral administration. The extended-release product will optimize therapeutic effect and safety of a drug at the same time improving the patient convenience and compliance¹. By incorporating the dose for 24 hrs into one tablet/capsule from which the drug is released slowly. This formulation helps to avoid the side effects associated with low and high concentrations. The ideal drug delivery system should show a constant zero-order release rate and maintain the constant plasma concentrations². The design of oral extended release delivery systems is subjected to several interrelated variables of considerable importance such as the type of delivery system, the disease being treated, the patient, the length of therapy and the properties of the drug³. Matrix tablets are considered to be the commercially feasible extended action dosage forms that involve the least processing variables, utilize the conventional facilities and accommodate large doses of drug. These remains an interest in developing novel formulations that allow for extended the drug release using readily available, inexpensive excipient by matrix-based formulation⁴.
⁵A tablet is a dosage form used in pharmaceuticals. It is made up of a powdered mixture of active ingredients and excipients that is pressed or compressed into a solid dosage. To facilitate efficient tableting, excipients can include diluents, binders or granulating agents, glidants (flow aids), and lubricants: disintegrate to encourage tablet break-up in the digestive tract; sweeteners or flavours to improve taste; and pigments to make the tablets visually appealing⁶. A polymer coating is frequently used to make tablets smoother and easier to swallow, to manage the active ingredient's release rate, to make them more resistant to the environment (increasing their shelf life), or to improve their look. Drug products designed to reduce the frequency of dosing by modifying the rate of drug absorption have been available for many years. Early modified release products were often intramuscular/ subcutaneous injections of suspensions of insoluble drug complexes, e.g., procaine penicillin, protamine zinc insulin, insulin zinc suspensions or injections of the drug in oil,⁷. Advances in technology have resulted in novel oral modified- release dosage forms. Many terms are used to describe modified-release products including extended-release, prolonged-release, controlled-release, controlled-delivery, slow release and sustained-release. Delayed-release Products are

modified-release, but they are not extended-release by definition. They entail the release of a discrete amount(s) of medicament after it has been administered. e.g., Enteric-coated products, have a lag time in which little or no absorption takes place⁸. While there are a variety of modified-release pharmaceuticals available as prescription and over-the-counter medications, only a small number have been proved to provide a therapeutic benefit. Rather for being designed for clinical benefit, several of the formulations appear to have been devised to extend patents or give a marketing advantage over conventional-release medications. Various prototype formulation trails were taken and assessed with various quality controls such as dissolving and assay to achieve these goals⁹. Extended release formulations make the drug available over extended time period after oral administration. The extended release product will optimize therapeutic effect and safety of a drug at the same time improving the patient convenience and compliance. By incorporating the dose for 24 hrs into one tablet/capsule from which the drug is released slowly¹⁰.

Tablets have been the most preferred oral dosage form for the patients suffering from chronic diseases like bronchial asthma, chronic bronchitis and chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD) because of low-cost therapy and ease of administration^{11,12}. The traditional tablets provide only a single and transient release of the drug. The pharmaceutical effect has only seen for the time duration in which the concentration of the drug remains within the therapeutic range that can be best achieved with ER tablets¹³. The significance of administering single-dose extended-release tablet that has discharged over an extended timeframe instead of multiple doses becomes the area of interest for the formulation designing scientists in the Pharmaceutical industry¹⁴. The oral prolonged discharge dosage form has been prepared for those medications that are comfortably absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), have a short half-life and eliminated quickly from the bloodstream¹⁵. The terms sustained action, sustained discharge, controlled discharge, timed release, prolonged action, depot, extended action and repository formulations have been used to represent the novel drug delivery system (NDDS) and formulated to get an extended therapeutic effect by continuously discharging drug over a prolonged time period after administration of a single dose¹⁶. There might be several other reasons also for the attractiveness of these dosage forms viz. provides enhanced bioavailability of medication, lessening in the recurrence of

administration to extend the timeframe of effective blood levels, reduces the fluctuation of the peak-trough level and adverse effects and possibly enhances the particular distribution of the medication¹⁷.

Extended-release formulations¹⁸⁻²¹ are the slow release drug so that plasma concentrations are maintained at a therapeutic level for a prolonged period of time (usually between 8 to 12 hours), drugs are metabolized before absorption either in the lumen (or) the tissues of the intestine, can show decreased bioavailability from the extended releasing system. These oral formulations are low-risk dose dumping, flexibility, of blending to attain difference release pattern as well as reproducible and short gastric residence time. Transfer of drug from one compartment to other if follows zero-order kinetic process then such drugs are a poor candidate for oral ER delivery system, it should be of first-order kinetics.²²

METHODOLOGY:

7.1. Analytical method development:

7.1.1 Determination of Wavelength:

10mg of pure drug was dissolved in 10ml methanol (primary stock solution - 1000 µg/ml). From this primary stock solution 1 ml was pipette out into 10 ml volumetric flask and made it up to 10ml with the media (Secondary stock solution - 100µg/ml). From secondary stock solution again 1ml was taken it in to another volumetric flask and made it up to 10 ml with media (working solution - 10µg/ml). The working solution was taken for determining the wavelength.

7.1.2 Determination of Calibration Curve:

10mg of pure drug was dissolved in 10ml methanol (primary stock solution - 1000 µg/ml). From this primary stock solution 1 ml was pipette out into 10 ml volumetric flask and made it up to 10ml with the media (Secondary stock solution - 100µg/ml). From secondary stock solution required concentrations were prepared (shown in Table 8.1 and 8.2) and those concentrations absorbance were found out at required wavelength.

7.2. Pre formulation parameters

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.

Angle of repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as, the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r \quad \tan \theta = \text{Angle of repose}$$

h = Height of the cone, r = Radius of the cone base

Table 7.1: Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density, is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. Bulk density is very important in the size of containers needed for handling, shipping, and storage of raw material and blend. It is also important in size blending equipment. 10 gm powder blend was sieved and introduced into a dry 20 ml cylinder, without compacting. The powder was carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled apparent volume, V_o, was read.

The bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M / V_o$$

Where, M = weight of sample

V_o = apparent volume of powder

Tapped density:

After carrying out the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until difference between succeeding measurement is less than 2 % and then tapped volume, V measured, to the nearest graduated

unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per L, using the formula:

$$\text{Tap} = M / V$$

Where, Tap= Tapped Density

M = Weight of sample

V= Tapped volume of powder

Measures of powder compressibility:

The Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. As such, it is measures of the relative importance of interparticulate interactions. In a free-flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value.

For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater interparticle interactions, and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities will be observed. These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\text{tap} - \text{b}) / \text{tap}] \times 100$$

Where, b = Bulk Density

Tap = Tapped Density

Hausner's ratio:

It is the ratio of tapped density to the bulk density. Hausner's found that this ratio was related to interparticle friction and, as such, could be used to predict powder flow properties. Generally a value less than 1.25 indicates good flow properties, which is equivalent to 20% of Carr's index.

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio} = \rho_{\text{tap}} / \rho_{\text{b}}$$

Where, ρ_{tap} = Tapped density.

ρ_{b} = Bulk density.

Table 7.4: Formulation composition for tablets

INGREDIENTS (MG)	FORMULATION							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Azilsartan	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Eudragit RL	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Ethyl Cellulose	25	50	75	100	-	-	-	-
Carbopol p934	-	-	-	-	25	50	75	100
Povidone	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Aerosil	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Magnesium Stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
MCC PH 102	QS	QS	QS	QS	QS	QS	QS	QS
Total weight(100)	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

All the quantities were in mg

Table 7.2: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Passable
2 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

7.3. Formulation development of Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Azilsartan. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 500mg.

Table 7.3: Ingredients categories

S.No	INGREDIENTS	USES
1.	Azilsartan	API
2.	Eudragit RL	Polymer
3.	Ethyl Cellulose	Polymer
4.	Carbopol p934	Polymer
5.	Povidone	Tablet disintegrant
6.	Aerosil	Anticaking agent
7.	Magnesium Stearate	Lubricant
8.	MCC PH 102	Adsorbent; Suspending agent

Procedure:

- 1) Azilsartan and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no \neq 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using direct compression method.

7.4. Evaluation of post compression parameters for prepared Tablets

The designed formulation tablets were studied for their physicochemical properties like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability and drug content.

Weight variation test:

To study the weight variation, twenty tablets were taken and their weight was determined individually and collectively on a digital weighing balance. The average weight of one tablet was determined from the collective weight. The weight variation test would be a satisfactory method of determining the drug content uniformity. Not more than two of the individual weights deviate from the average weight by more than the percentage shown in the following table and none deviate by more than twice the percentage. The mean and deviation were determined. The percent deviation was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Deviation} = (\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight} / \text{Average weight}) \times 100$$

Table 7.5: Pharmacopoeial specifications for tablet weight variation

Average weight of tablet (mg) (I.P)	Average weight of tablet (mg) (U.S.P)	Maximum percentage difference allowed
Less than 80	Less than 130	10
80-250	130-324	7.5
More than	More than 324	5

Hardness:

Hardness of tablet is defined as the force applied across the diameter of the tablet in order to break the tablet. The resistance of the tablet to chipping, abrasion or breakage under condition of storage transformation and handling before usage depends on its hardness. For each formulation, the hardness of three tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester and the average is calculated and presented with deviation.

Thickness:

Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Average thickness for core and coated tablets is calculated and presented with deviation.

Friability:

It is measured of mechanical strength of tablets. Roche friabilator was used to determine the friability by following procedure. Pre weighed tablets were placed in the friabilator. The tablets were rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes (100 rotations). At the end of test, the tablets were re weighed, loss in the weight of tablet is the measure of friability and is expressed in percentage as

$$\% \text{ Friability} = [(W1-W2) / W] \times 100$$

Where, W1 = Initial weight of three tablets

W2 = Weight of the three tablets after testing

Determination of drug content:

Tablets were tested for their drug content. Ten tablets were finely powdered quantities of the powder equivalent to one tablet weight of drug were accurately weighed, transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 50 ml water and were allowed to stand to

ensure complete solubility of the drug. The mixture was made up to volume with media. The solution was suitably diluted and the absorption was determined by UV –Visible spectrophotometer. The drug concentration was calculated from the calibration curve.

In vitro drug release studies

Dissolution parameters:

Apparatus	--	USP-II,
Paddle Method		
Dissolution Medium	--	0.1 N
HCl, pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer		
RPM	--	50
Sampling intervals (hrs)	--	
		1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12
Temperature	--	37°C ± 0.5°C

Procedure:

900ml Of 0.1 HCl was placed in vessel and the USP apparatus –II (Paddle Method) was assembled. The medium was allowed to equilibrate to temp of 37°C ± 0.5°C. Tablet was placed in the vessel and apparatus was operated for 2 hours and then the media 0.1 N HCl were removed and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added process was continued up to 12 hrs at 50 rpm. At definite time intervals withdrawn 5 ml of sample, filtered and again 5ml media was replaced. Suitable dilutions were done with media and analyzed by spectrophotometrically at required wavelength using UV-spectrophotometer.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Zero order release rate kinetics:

To study the zero-order release kinetics the release rate data are fitted to the following equation.

$$F = K_0 t$$

Where, 'F' is the drug release at time 't', and 'K₀' is the zero order release rate constant. The plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First order release rate kinetics: The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\text{Log } (100-F) = kt$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted then it gives first order release.

Higuchi release model: To study the Higuchi release kinetics, the release rate data were fitted to the following equation.

$$F = k t^{1/2}$$

Where, 'k' is the Higuchi constant.

In Higuchi model, a plot of % drug release versus square root of time is linear.

Korsmeyer and Peppas release model:

The mechanism of drug release was evaluated by plotting the log percentage of drug released versus log time according to Korsmeyer- Peppas equation. The exponent 'n' indicates the mechanism of drug release calculated through the slope of the straight Line.

$$M_t / M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where, M_t / M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time 't',

k represents a constant, and 'n' is the diffusional exponent, which characterizes the type of release mechanism during the dissolution process. For non-Fickian release, the value of n falls between 0.5 and 1.0; while in case of Fickian diffusion, n = 0.5; for zero-order release (case I transport), n=1; and for supercase II transport, n > 1. In this model, a plot of log (M_t / M_∞) versus log (time) is linear.

Hixson-Crowell release model:

$$(100-Q_t)^{1/3} = 100^{1/3} - K_{HC}t$$

Where, k is the Hixson-Crowell rate constant.

Hixson-Crowell model describes the release of drugs from an insoluble matrix through mainly erosion. (Where there is a change in surface area and diameter of particles or tablets).

7.5. Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The compatibility between the pure drug and excipients was detected by FTIR spectra obtained on Bruker FTIR Germany (Alpha T). The solid powder sample directly placed on yellow crystal which was made up of ZnSe. The spectra were recorded over the wave number of 4000 cm⁻¹ to 400cm⁻¹.

8.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The present study was aimed to developing extended release tablets of Azilsartan using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and *in vitro* drug release studies.

8.1. Analytical Method

Graphs of Azilsartan were taken in 0.1N HCl and in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 248 nm and 253 nm respectively.

Table 8.1: Observations for graph of Azilsartan in 0.1N HCl (248 nm)

Conc. [µg/ml]	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.125
10	0.231
15	0.334
20	0.458
25	0.561

Figure 8.1: Standard graph of Azilsartan in 0.1N HCl

Table 8.2: Observations for graph of Azilsartan in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (253nm)

Concentration [µg/ml]	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.134
10	0.252
15	0.357
20	0.492
25	0.599

Figure 8.2: Standard graph of Azilsartan pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (253 nm)

8.3. Pre formulation parameters of powder blend

Table 8.3: Pre-formulation parameters of Core blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
N1	26.05±0.65	0.307	0.444	13.46	1.16
N2	25.94±0.56	0.384	0.434	17.85	1.22
N3	26.02±0.61	0.267	0.307	13.33	1.15
N4	26.21±0.93	0.346	0.404	14.35	1.16
N5	26.28±0.33	0.323	0.376	14.09	1.16
N6	25.81±0.61	0.393	0.453	13.24	1.15
N7	26.10±0.53	0.318	0.368	13.58	1.16
N8	26.21±0.32	0.312	0.358	12.84	1.15

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.267 to 0.393 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.307 to 0.453 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be below 17.85 which show that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the hausner ratio below 1.22 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

8.4. Quality Control parameters for tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression coated tablet.

8.4. In-vitro quality control parameters for tablets

Formulation codes	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
N1	499.36	4.1	0.86	5.15	97.10
N2	497.25	4.5	0.64	5.69	99.91
N3	497.62	4.7	0.53	5.14	98.68
N4	500.04	4.9	0.42	5.55	99.42
N5	498.12	4.0	0.54	5.20	100.13
N6	496.74	4.2	0.45	5.48	99.71
N7	498.37	4.9	0.36	5.92	97.82
N8	499.86	4.0	0.24	5.48	96.86

Weight variation test:

Tablets of each batch were subjected to weight variation test, difference in weight and percent deviation was calculated for each tablet and was shown in the Table 8.4. The average weight of the tablet is approximately in range of 496.74 to 500.04 mg, so the permissible limit is ±7.5% (>500 mg). The results of the test showed that, the tablet weights were within the pharmacopoeia limit.

Hardness test:

Hardness of the three tablets of each batch was checked by using Pfizer hardness tester and the data's were shown in Table 8.4. The results showed that the hardness of the tablets is in range of 4.0 to 4.9 kg/cm², which was within IP limits.

Thickness:

Thickness of three tablets of each batch was checked by using Micrometer and data shown in Table-8.4. The result showed that thickness of the tablet is raging from 5.14 to 5.92 mm.

Friability:

Tablets of each batch were evaluated for percentage friability and the data were shown in the Table 8.4. The average friability of all the formulations was less than 1% as per official requirement of IP indicating a good mechanical resistance of tablets.

Drug content:

Drug content studies were performed for the prepared formulations. From the drug content studies it was concluded that all the formulations were showing the % drug content values within 96.86-100.13 %.

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be

within limits.

8.5. In-Vitro Drug release studies

Table 8.5: Dissolution data of Azilsartan tablets

TIME (H)	CUMULATIVE % OF DRUG RELEASE							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	20.25	15.42	14.62	12.62	27.04	24.65	15.42	14.62
2	37.26	24.73	19.86	15.86	35.69	32.59	24.73	19.86
3	42.16	39.63	25.35	23.35	41.46	38.34	39.63	25.35
4	58.01	48.04	30.45	28.45	56.97	43.40	48.04	30.45
5	68.26	57.25	39.8	36.08	62.54	58.29	53.25	39.85
6	77.19	66.33	47.25	42.25	79.06	64.85	57.33	47.25
7	82.64	70.41	58.24	50.24	85.39	70.22	63.41	58.24
8	98.19	85.84	65.73	68.73	97.93	78.78	71.84	65.73
9		90.8	71.34	77.34		85.46	76.08	71.34
10		97.35	87.52	81.52		93.34	81.26	77.52
11			98.17	96.17		98.27	90.14	80.17
12				99.18			96.72	89.81

Fig 8.3: Dissolution profile of Azilsartan (F1 to F4 formulations)

Fig8.4: Dissolution profile of Azilsartan (F5 to F8 formulations)

Fig 8.5: Dissolution profile of Azilsartan (F1-F8 formulations)

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Table 8.6: Release kinetics data for optimised formulation

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
12.62	1	1.000	1.101	0.000	1.941	12.620	0.0792	-0.899	87.38	4.642	4.437	0.204
15.86	2	1.414	1.200	0.301	1.925	7.930	0.0631	-0.800	84.14	4.642	4.382	0.260
23.35	3	1.732	1.368	0.477	1.885	7.783	0.0428	-0.632	76.65	4.642	4.248	0.394
28.45	4	2.000	1.454	0.602	1.855	7.113	0.0351	-0.546	71.55	4.642	4.151	0.490
36.08	5	2.236	1.557	0.699	1.806	7.216	0.0277	-0.443	63.92	4.642	3.998	0.643
42.25	6	2.449	1.626	0.778	1.762	7.042	0.0237	-0.374	57.75	4.642	3.865	0.776
50.24	7	2.646	1.701	0.845	1.697	7.177	0.0199	-0.299	49.76	4.642	3.678	0.963
68.73	8	2.828	1.837	0.903	1.495	8.591	0.0145	-0.163	31.27	4.642	3.150	1.491
77.34	9	3.000	1.888	0.954	1.355	8.593	0.0129	-0.112	22.66	4.642	2.830	1.812
81.52	10	3.162	1.911	1.000	1.267	8.152	0.0123	-0.089	18.48	4.642	2.644	1.998
96.17	11	3.317	1.983	1.041	0.583	8.743	0.0104	-0.017	3.83	4.642	1.565	3.077
99.18	12	3.464	1.996	1.079	-0.086	8.265	0.0101	-0.004	0.82	4.642	0.936	3.706

Fig 8.6 : Zero order release kinetics graph

Fig 8.7 : Higuchi release kinetics graph

Fig 8.8: Kars mayer peppas graph

Fig 8.9: First order release kinetics graph

From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation F4 was followed Zero order release kinetics.

8.2. Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy:

Figure 8.10: FT-TR Spectrum of Azilsartan pure drug.

Figure 8.11: FT-IR Spectrum of Optimised Formulation

9. CONCLUSION:

The present study concludes that Extended drug delivery of Azilsartan tablets can be a good way to prolong duration of action of drug by reducing the frequency of dosing of Azilsartan. Present study concludes that extended drug delivery system should be a suitable method for Azilsartan administration. The optimised formulation was found to be F4 formulation.

All formulations were found to be satisfactory when evaluated for thickness, average weight, hardness, friability, drug content uniformity and *In vitro* drug release.

The *in vitro* drug release in optimized formulation F4 was found to be 99.18% in 12hrs. The optimized formulation F4 also showed satisfactory hardness, Friability, drug content, weight variation.

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